

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Update 1: Data and Research data Management Plan (DMP/RDMP)

**Funded by
the European Union**

DISCLAIMER

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon -WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 research and innovation programme.

Disclaimer- "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Document overview

Project Acronym:	DIAMAS
Project Name:	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
Project No:	101058007
Start Date:	1/09/2022
End Date:	31/09/2025
Contributing WP	WP1
WP Leader:	AMU
Deliverable identifier:	D1.5
Contractual Delivery Date: 10/2022	Actual Delivery Date: 10/2023
Nature: Report	Version: 1.0
Dissemination level	PU
Deliverable status	Approved by the European Commission

Version history

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
1.0	Oct. 2023	Updated version of the D1.1 "Data and Research data Management Plan (DMP/RDMP)"

Table of Contents

Document overview	2
Version history	3
Table of Contents	3
Executive Summary	4
Method	5
Content	6
Reuse of previous data	6
Data generated by the project	9
Findable	13
Accessible	17
Interoperable	23
Reusable	25
Costs, Security and Ethics	28
Consortium overview	30

Executive Summary

In the transition towards Open Access (OA), institutional publishing is challenged by fragmentation and varying service quality, visibility, and sustainability. To address this issue, DIAMAS gathers 23 organisations from 12 European countries, well-versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. The project will: 1. Map the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in 25 countries of the ERA with special attention for IPSPs that do not charge fees for publishing or reading. This will yield a taxonomy of IPSPs and an IPSP landscape report, a basis for the rest of the project. 2. Coordinate and improve the efficiency and quality of IPSPs by developing a European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). This quality seal will professionalise, strengthen and reduce the fragmentation of institutional publishing in Europe. EQSIP will serve as a benchmark for a gap analysis of the data.

The DMP/RDMP outlines how data are to be handled (secured, stored, accessed, preserved) both during the project, and after the project is completed.

Method

The project Data Management Plan was prepared following the guidelines provided by the European Commission in the “Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template v. 1.0 5 may 2021” mentioned in the “Program Guide Horizon Europe 2.0 11 April 2022”¹.

All questions in the template were distributed in a collaborative online spreadsheet that all partners can update at any moment. The DMP can be updated in real time and a “history of changes” allows to record the changes in the document (content, author, date). Updates on the DMP are discussed as a standing point every two weeks in the agenda of the WP Leaders meeting, and regular snapshots are made of the live document to be delivered to the European Commission.

The live DMP is built upon several tabs :

- (1) Reuse of previous data
- (2) Data generated by the project
- (3) Findability
- (4) Accessibility
- (5) Interoperability
- (6) Reuse
- (7) Costs, Security and Ethics

The data generated by the project are identified with internal identifiers based on the identification of the work packages, e.g. “DS 1.2” can be read as : “dataset number 2 from work package number 1”. The tabs 2 to 7 are interlinked around the identified datasets.

¹ Available here :

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf The link to the DMP template in this document is broken and neither documents have any PID, which indicates that the European Commission does not apply to itself its own recommendations.

Content

Reuse of previous data

Name	PID or link	License	For	Remarks
OA Diamond Journals Study. Dataset	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4553103	CC0	WP2	
DOAJ journal metadata	https://doaj.org/public-data-dump/journal	CC BY-SA 4.0	WP2	Will be downloaded at some point. License is DOAJ's. Data description will be based on earlier version in https://doi.org/10.18710/LHRTP9/RZWA2C
Web of Science journal metadata	https://clarivate.com/	no open license	WP2	
Dimensions journal metadata	https://www.dimensions.ai/	no open license	WP2	
Scopus journal metadata	https://www.scopus.com/home.uri	no open license	WP2	
Lens journal metadata	https://www.lens.org/	uncertain	WP2	Uncertain licence, see https://about.lens.org/policies/#acceptableuse
ISSN registry journal metadata	https://portal.issn.org/	no open license	WP2	
ISSN registry (ROAD dataset) journal metadata	https://road.issn.org/	no open license	WP3	
Unpaywall/Unsub OA journals identification list	Help annotate society and...	Waiting for response from owner	WP2	

Name	PID or link	License	For	Remarks
Polish list	Arianta	Owner allows us CC0	WP2	
Swiss list	List of Platinum OA Journals in Switzerland	CC0	WP2	
German list	Diamond Open Access Journals Germany (DOAG)	CC BY 4.0	WP2	
Journal data for European scholarly journals	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7180290		WP 2	Data produced as part of this study: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5909512 . Journals identified through Ulrichsweb, matched to DOAJ and ISSN Gold datasets
CrossRef Metadata	Metadata Plus - Crossref	licensed by UGOE, need to check back with CrossRef about terms of use	WP 2	
PKP dataset 202111 matched to ROAD, DOAJ (for sharing)	PKP dataset 202111 matc...	Unknown	WP2	Dataset owned by Bianca Kramer which compares PKP data with ROAD, DOAJ etc.
PKP raw dataset		Unknown	WP2	Raw dataset from PKP - either public version or from Mark Huskisson
ROR	Research Organization Registry	CC0	WP2	

Name	PID or link	License	For	Remarks
Scholia	Scholia	CC0	WP2	
Openaire Explore	OpenAIRE EXPLORE	CC BY	WP2	
OpenAire research graph (dump)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3516917	CC BY	WP2	
Publication Forum register	Julkaisufoorumi	Unknown	WP2	
ERIH Plus	Search ERIH PLUS NSD	Unknown	WP2	
Norwegian register	Search in Norwegian List Norwegian Register	CC BY 4.0	WP2	Licence according to info from data owner 31.10.2022
Croatian list - HRČAK	Alphabetical journals list	Unknown	WP2	Metadata usage defined at https://hrcak.srce.hr/en/politike

Data generated by the project

N.B. DS2.3, DS4.1, DS5.1 are in red and orange to flag the uncertainties (high and medium) at this stage concerning the management of these data

Internal Id	Description	WP	Provenance	Type	Format	Size	Purpose (relation to objectives)	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	WP1	Project	Text	Gdocs	<1GB	n/a	none	
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	WP1	Project	Text	PDF	<1GB	all	See PEDR	
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	WP1	Project	Text	PDF	<1GB	n/a	EC auditors	
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	WP2	Qualtrics	Text, tabular	csv	<1GB	SO1	Information and library science researchers	https://www.qualtrics.com/ Provided by EUA
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	WP2	DOAJ, Knowledge Exchange, OADJS	List	txt	<1GB	SO1	Capacity Centre, scientific information service providers	The list will become rapidly obsolete after its first iteration. There is no plan at the moment to transform it as a maintained database.
DS2.3	IPSPs database	WP2	Output of DS2.1	List/database	csv and potential web formats	<1GB	SO1	Capacity Centre, OPERAS PSP service	Database will be defined by the typology of IPSPs and the results of the survey. Use to be defined by WP4

Internal Id	Description	WP	Provenance	Type	Format	Size	Purpose (relation to objectives)	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	WP2	Output of DS2.1	dataset	csv	<1GB	SO1	none - cleaned dataset used for analysis, not for reuse	Cleaned data - the dataset cleaned for analysis including translations into English of free text responses, addition of columns showing geographical region and de-duplication of responses. Although further cleaning/refining is expected during the analysis, this is the final dataset to be used in the D2.3 Landscape Report
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	WP2	Output of DS2.1	dataset	csv			researchers, funders, policy makers	Anonymised data - a copy of the cleaned data that has been fully anonymised, checked and deposited in Zenodo with a CC0 licence. This dataset will include a cleaned set of data from the Turkish IPSP data
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	WP3	Project	Text, tabular	csv, ods	<1GB	SO2	researchers, funders, policy makers	The analysis of quality criteria for journals and platforms contained in policy, funding and other documents, conducted in T3.1 IPSP best practices overview, will be performed using structured analysis sheets, which will contain relevant information extracted from the analyzed documents. Once the analysis is completed, the sheets will be converted into a tabular format.
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	WP4	Project	List	csv	<1GB	SO3	IPSPs	List of training materials, guidelines, toolkits and other resources available via the Common Access Point, collected by the project partners. It is not decided yet if it will be open to external contributions and how.
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up	WP 5	Qualtrics	Text, tabular	csv	<1GB	SO4	researchers, funders, policy makers	Provisional. The usage of Qualtrics for this survey is not confirmed yet.

Internal Id	Description	WP	Provenance	Type	Format	Size	Purpose (relation to objectives)	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
	survey:								
DS5.2	National case studies of IPSP activity	WP 5	Project	Text	txt	<1GB	SO4	researchers, funders, policy makers	
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	WP 5	Project	Text	txt	<1GB	SO4	IPSPs, funders, institutions, policy makers	
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	WP7	Project	Text, images, videos	xml, png, pdf, mp4	<1TB	all	researchers, funders, policy makers, general public, media, .	
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	WP7	Project	Text, images, videos	xml, png, PDF, mp4, printed material	<1TB	all	researchers, funders, policy makers, general public, media, .	
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview	WP7	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	all	none	To complete stakeholder engagement tasks, personal data will be collected and stored throughout the project. This basic personal data will ensure stakeholders are managed and engaged throughout the project, as envisaged in the DOA. No contact details (e.g. emails, etc) will be

Findable

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	none		FALSE	FALSE
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	none	none	FALSE	FALSE
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS2.3	IPSPs database	n/a	n/a	FALSE	FALSE
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	not for public use	none	FALSE	FALSE
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	DOI	n/aMARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up survey:	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS5.2	National case studies of IPSP activity	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	DOI	MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org)	TRUE	TRUE

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	none	none	TRUE	TRUE
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	none	none	TRUE	TRUE
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview		none	FALSE	FALSE

Accessible

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	none	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	Document confidential for the internal management of the project and EC audit	n/a	Login/Password	Project Manager	n/a	n/a	5 years after the end of the project	5 years after the end of the project	no	no
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	n/a	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a		CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	none	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	Document confidential for the internal management of the project and EC audit	n/a	Login/Password	Project Manager	n/a	n/a	5 years after the end of the project	5 years after the end of the project	no	no
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	Only the anonymised dataset will be made available (GDPR)	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	n/a	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset PID	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS2.3	IPSPs database		FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	n/a	HTTPS, API tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	none	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	Cleaned dataset will not be made public due to GDPR	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	none	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE			n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	Accompanying documentation on Zenodo (when ready - early 2024)

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	n/a	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	n/a	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up survey:	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	Only the anonymised dataset will be made available (GDPR)	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no
DS5.2	National case studies	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	n/a	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	undefined	undefined	no	no

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
	of IPSP activity														
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	Zenodo	FALSE	TRUE	TRUE	Only the anonymised dataset will be made available (GDPR)	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	underfined	undefined	no	no
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	none	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE		HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	End of the project	End of the project	no	no

Internal ID	Description	Repository	Specific Arrangement with repository?	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Will the data be made openly available?	If not, why (legal and contractual restrictions)	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data)	Duration of availability (metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	none	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE		HTTPS	n/a	n/a	n/a	CC0	End of the project	End of the project	no	no
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview	none		FALSE	FALSE	GDPR		login/password	Project Manager	n/a	n/a	End of the project	End of the project	no	no

Interoperable

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	n/a	n/a	n/a
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	Dublin Core	n/a	Shared Community in Zenodo
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	n/a	n/a	n/a
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS2.3	IPSPs database	tbd	tbd	tbd
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	n/a	n/a	n/a
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	tbd	tbd	tbd
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up survey:	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS5.2	National case studies of IPSP activity	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	Dublin Core	n/a	n/a
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	none	no	no
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	none	no	no
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview	none	no	no

Reusable

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accesible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	QRMP	n/a	EC auditors	FALSE	
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	n/a	CC BY	yes	FALSE	External Review. See QRMP
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	QRMP	n/a	EC auditors	FALSE	internal audit
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	Qualtrics documentation	CC:BY	yes	TRUE	Manual quality assessment will be performed on random samples
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	Readme file	CC BY	yes	FALSE	Manual quality assessment of random samples
DS2.3	IPSPs database	tbd	tbd	yes	FALSE	tbd
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	Internal use only	n/a	no	FALSE	Data cleaning outlined in D2.4 Landscape report

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accesible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	Accompanying documentation on Zenodo	CC0	yes	FALSE	Data cleaning outlined in D2.4 Landscape report
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	Readme file	CC BY	yes	TRUE	To minimize misinterpretation risk, translations made by native speakers will be provided. Control checks will be performed: the same documents will be independently analyzed by multiple individuals.
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	Readme file	CC BY	yes	FALSE	Manual quality assessment of random samples
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up survey:	Qualtrics documentation	CC BY	yes	TRUE	Manual quality assessment will be performed on random samples
DS5.2	National case studies of IPSP activity	Readme file	CC BY	yes	FALSE	External Review. See QRMP

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	Readme file	CC BY	yes	FALSE	n/a
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	no	CC BY	No	FALSE	Proofreading, internal reviews
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	PEDR	CC BY	Yes	FALSE	Proofreading, internal reviews
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview	no	n/a	No	FALSE	Internal review

Costs, Security and Ethics

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	n/a	OpenEdition Google Drive and EZGED 3.3 provided by PVM	none	none	GDPR
DS1.2	Projects deliverables	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	n/a	OpenEdition Google Drive and EZGED 3.3 provided by PVM	none	none	Confidentiality on financial data
DS2.1	IPSP survey data	n/a	EUA Qualtrics and Zenodo	Zenodo	none	GDPR : the dataset will be anonymised prior to public release
DS2.2	Diamond Journals	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none
DS2.3	IPSPs database	tbd	tbd	tbd	none	tbd
DS2.4	IPSP survey data - cleaned	n/a	OpenEdition Google Drive and EZGED 3.3 provided by PVM	none	none	Cleaned dataset will not be made public due to GDPR
DS2.5	IPSP survey data - anonymised	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS3.1	Analysis of IPSP best practices	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none
DS4.1	Registry of training resources	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none
DS5.1	Web survey responses from IPSP follow-up survey:	n/a	EUA Qualtrics and Zenodo	Zenodo	none	GDPR : the dataset will be anonymised prior to public release
DS5.2	National case studies of IPSP activity	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	none
DS5.3	Interview material for task 5.2 "Identify areas of potential collaboration"	n/a	Zenodo	Zenodo	none	GDPR : the dataset will be anonymised prior to public release
DS7.1	Project website and the information contained therein.	See GA	Liber Wordpress	none	none	none
DS7.2	Project dissemination material	See GA	Liber Wordpress	none	none	none
DS7.3	Internal stakeholder overview	n/a	OpenEdition Google Drive	none	none	GDPR

Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES

Update 1: DMP/RDMP

UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL

EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK